

Politicization of Employment and Service Delivery in Obingwa and Ohafia Local Governments in Abia State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Foundational principles of public Service laid down by scholars such as Woodrow Wilson and Max Weber, emphasized merit-based recruitment and political neutrality. Recent studies on public sector employment in Nigeria have primarily focused on federal and state levels, often overlooking the dynamics at the local government level. Specifically, there is limited empirical research on how politicization of employment affects service delivery and staff welfare in rural local government areas such as Obingwa and Ohafia in Abia State. However, in Obingwa and Ohafia Local Governments, the politicization of employment practices, including the filling of positions with ghost workers, has significantly affected the efficiency and welfare of the Local Government employees. This study therefore investigated the politicization of employment and service delivery in Obingwa and Ohafia Local Government Areas of Abia State.

The study employed survey research design, with the population of 2,291. Three hundred and twenty-six (326) employees were randomly sampled in Ohafia and Obingwa Local Government Areas of Abia State, using Taro Yamane's formula. Structured questionnaire was used as an instrument of data collection and was analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS). Hypotheses were tested using chi-square at 5% significant level.

The study found that recruitment policy has positively influenced service delivery (Chi Square = 81.76 p-value < 0.05), while political interference in recruitment process has significantly reduced employees' efficiency and, consequently, service delivery (Chi Square = 81.37 p-value < 0.05). Furthermore, a major contending pressure identified was the prevalence of ghost workers who, despite not contributing to the workload, yet continue to draw salaries, leaving the real workers overburden (Chi Square = 43.67 p-value < 0.05). Finally, it was found that there is significant workable solution that can lead to merit-based employment to curb such politicized practices (Chi Square = 94.00 p-value < 0.05).

The study therefore concluded that the politicization of employment compounded by issues like delayed salaries and ghost workers phenomenon which have directly affected their efficiency and the quality of services provided to the community. The study recommended that Local Governments should adopt merit-based recruitment process, including the use of external assessment panels, personnel database, biometric machines and feedback mechanism.

Keyword: Politicization, Employment, Public service, Service delivery, Local Government.

Word Count: 297

Introduction

Woodrow Wilson the founding father of Public Administration emphasized the need for a professional, merit-based and politically neutral bureaucracy. His early writings contributed that elected officials should stop intervening in determining the detailed decisions made by administrators (Svara 2020). Governmental process lies in two central themes known as policy-making and policy-execution. Policy-making is the role of the political leaders while policy-execution is the business of public servants. Gouglas (2023) ascertained that in countries like, France and Belgium, ministerial cabinet who serve as political advisory, work with career civil servants and this is done to allow public service employees to mirror existing expertise and avoiding the political leaders not to takeover employment criteria in the public service. Nkgapele and Mofokeng (2021) observed in South African public service that, Merit-based recruitment is crucial for meeting the public service's needs and achieving employment equity by making opportunities accessible to all societal groups. While the practical application of merit-based recruitment presents opportunities, it still encounters considerable obstacles, such as political interference, and fragile institutional structures.

Yaro (2019) opined that proper recruitment exercise decision is translated into the function of Local Government Service Commission as an agency responsible for the recruitment, promotion, career development, discipline, processing of contributory pension fund, of the local government staff and public servants in the local government. Yaro (2019) further asserted that the pivotal function of the commission is to recruit on merit basis, permanent staff which should not be interfered by the politicians because the elected political officers in their own way, make appointment to various offices, like special advisers for the convenience of their office who would act as their eye in various offices and this is done for them not to have hand in the recruitment of permanent staff of the public service.

However, in 2020, employment in Obingwa Local Government took a different dimension when the then Local Government chairman sacked employees of Obingwa indiscriminately and replaced them with his political cronies whom he single-handedly placed on payroll to be selling tickets for tri-cycle riders (Ofurum, 2022). Francis (2019) investigated that as of May 2019, Abia State Government did not pay the health workers including those at the local government for about 13 months. Based on the above anomalies, the service delivery such as health, road, and school would be affected. It becomes maladministration when they infringe and cast their interest into process of employment of permanent staff of the government who are employed for the continuity of government policies, service delivery, career development and are always there to serve them and various other incoming political officials. Employees have rights and protections that come from principles of public service and even labour laws. Public servants and elected politicians are two crucial actors in the government. Politicians are seen as sovereign representatives of political interest while the public servants are seen as subordinate policy executors and their major concern is efficiency and efficiency is the only means to reach the public interest (Panday, 2017). From all angle of view, if the employment is politicized, efficiency which leads to service delivery would crumble down. To maintain service delivery, there is need for advocacy of impartial proficiency.

Aguoru (2018) observed that each local government was allocated 50 slots for employment with a directive to the council chairmen to accept only recommendations for employment through the stake holders within their local governments at the ratio of 35 for school certificate holders into grade level 1 to 6, while the state will handle the recruitment of graduates into level 7 and above also on testimonial from party stalwarts and government officials. The question that comes to mind is, if the government that has been complaining of over bloated labour force and huge wage bill as reasons for their inability to meet up with monthly salary payments and council staff, secondary and primary school teachers, pensioners and workers in parastatals and agencies are still being owed from three months and above, what is the economic balance in recruiting more staff if you are unable to pay those already in your employment, when employment slots have already been given out to council chairmen with a directive, is it not fraudulent asking gullible Abians to make payments for employment when the employment has been concluded through the hands of stalwarts.

As a result, the citizens will be unattended because when political head who should do the work of watchdog has become a source of encouragement to ghost workers, then the service delivery will lie in the hands of few available staff whose salaries are equally delayed. When employment is not based on merit, is prone to many cases of unethical practices which affects the behavior of the public servants and at large affects the lives of the citizens.

Considering many complexities of the situation where Ohafia and Obingwa Local Government Areas are suffering lack of service delivery, irrespective of abundance revenue made from enormous trade and businesses from the area, even from the village women in the market, Okada riders and various transportations, yet the area suffers endemic backwardness in terms, poor health facilities, poor state of primary schools and bad roads. Local Government employment in Ohafia and Obingwa Local Government Areas, is moving in an opposite direction. The nature of employment in these aforementioned local governments have turned to overt partisan politicization and a system of recruitment and promotions on the basis of declared political loyalty. It is against this background that this study tends to examine politicization of employment and service delivery in Obingwa and Ohafia local governments in Abia State, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study examined the politicization of employment on service delivery in Ohafia and Obingwa Local Government Areas. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. determine the extent to which recruitment policy promotes service delivery in the two local governments under investigation;
2. examine the contending pressures faced by the public servants in the local governments and its implications on service delivery;
3. identify workable propositions/solutions that would lead to merit-based employment.

Review of Literature

Politicization

Bashir (2025) views politicization as the political leader's interference with decision making in public administrative matters such as, planning, organizing, staffing, directing, coordinating,

reporting, and budgeting as well as allocation and use of public funds. Local government's problem is the political influence on the personnel management, leading to the politicization of appointments and general human resource management. Halligan (2021) observes that Politicization covers various mechanisms through which political actors seek to influence public administration. This includes recruiting individuals to government positions based on political contemplations (patronage) and employing understated methods to shape the behaviour of public servants.

Bashir (2025) in his study on Impact of Politicization of State Government on Personnel Management of Local Government Staff in Nigeria. This research highlights how state government politicization affects local government personnel management. The study identified that appointments are often based on political affiliations rather than merit. This politicization results in inadequate staffing, lack of training, and the appointment of unqualified personnel. Consequently, service delivery is compromised, benefiting the political class at the expense of effective governance.

According to Peter et al (2022), politicization of public service employment is the ability of the politicians to influence employment which is strategically biased and, in a manner to benefit the incumbent rather than the citizens. Halligan (2021). states that politicization of public service employment is synonymous with violation of the principles of political neutrality of public servants. Kim, Jung and Kim. (2022) argued that scholars have underscored the implications of politicization of public service employment, which among other things, non-merit recruitment which has resulted to the prevalence of other corrupt practices, politicians inclination to employ base on party affiliation and to woo voters with government funds or, alternatively, develop programmatic politics, (choosing a particular area to establish government programme without due process). Politicization of employment has eaten deep in the veins of the politicians that employees are very likely to a large extent owe their employment to political interference rather than competence, Mugellini et al (2021).

Service Delivery

Hartanti, Abawajy, and Chowdhury, (2022) opined that service delivery as the provision of goods and other life support amenities by government to maximize the welfare and well-being of the people. Rosenbloom, *et al* (2022), contended that service delivery is the relationship that exists between policy makers, service providers and the populace, and it consists social services that enhance personal security and public interest, and examples of these services of public interest include: security, education, energy, water, public transport and healthcare. These are generally referred to as state responsibility. Onyekwelu (2023) argues that service delivery is the process of getting the needs of citizens through prompt and efficient procedures.

Theoretical Review

Efficiency Service Theory

William Mackenzie and Sharpe are the proponents of efficiency service theory in 18th Centuries. These scholars argued that the purpose of Local Government is to provide services that are locally characterized and to cater for the needs of the people at the grassroots. For instance, the need to maintain local roads, provision of pipe-borne water, and health centers, etc., (Ajulor and Ibikunle, 2021). Local Government exists to provide basic essential services and as such, service delivery to the Local people is expected to pre-occupy the resources, power, time of the Local Government. Jim Sharpe(1970) argued that the efficient performance of these services is so compelling that if Local Government did not exist, something else would have to be created in its place.

Efficiency Service theory acknowledged that certain services are better performed by the Local Government and with financial wherewithal. In line with the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria as amended, Section four made provisions for the functions of Local Government which are to be performed by the tier of government. The same Constitution, in Section 162(6, 7 and 8) made provision for statutory allocations. Local Government stated that 10 percent of state internally generated revenue must be allotted to the Local Government. These are to strengthen the councils financially to execute those noble functions and facilitate development. However political interference by the state government had hampered this cause. Therefore, Local Government are characterized with non-performance (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999).

Though the theory advocated that certain services be executed by the Local Government and must be supported with financial provisions, however, one of the major critics of the theory especially to its application is on lack of local government autonomy in Nigeria. The Federal Government recently filed a lawsuit against 36 states Governors at the Supreme court, seeking an order to allow federation allocation to be credited directly to the account of the councils. As a matter of fact, the state governors have capitalized on this loophole to impose appointees who are loyal to their principal to manage the councils and this is to the detriment of people who should be the beneficiaries of the developmental services that is meant to be provided however, one of the major critics of the theory especially to its application is on lack of local government autonomy in Nigeria (Premium Times, 2024).

Empirical Review

Employment in the Local Government System

The effectiveness of public service is on provision of social services. However, there are challenges that are evident in areas such as employment practices, service delivery, and institutional governance, especially at the local government level. Maqoko and Asmah-Andoh (2019) highlighted conflicts between politicians and administrators in the Nelson Mandela Bay Municipality, negatively impacting social service delivery. In contrast, Njunwa (2020) study in Morogoro Municipality found that cooperation between elected and appointed officials can enhance project implementation, suggesting that while tensions can arise from overlapping roles, effective collaboration is possible when challenges are addressed., In the study, correlation

coefficient was used to empirically prove that presentation (politics) as appointment criteria has no benefit in efficiency service delivery and national development. The study discovered that the objective of representation in appointment is to promote national unity and integration.

Egboh, Obiorah and Mokwunyei, (2023) in their study on Federal Character and Service Delivery in Nigeria, it was empirically identified that, politics is the major problem facing recruitment in the Nigeria Public Sector. The study revealed that the politicization of appointment in the public sector have created difficulties for the appointment of right persons for the right jobs based on the principles of merit and equal opportunities for all citizens. Okon and Inyang (2023) conducted research specifically in local governments in southern Nigeria, including parts of Abia State. Their study found that political interference in employment decisions and the proliferation of ghost workers significantly hindered administrative efficiency and service provision. The researchers recommended greater autonomy for local governments and institutional safeguards to protect employment processes from political capture.

Ajani, and Oyekola, (2021) in their study, which showed that respondents had a negative perception of public service in Nigeria both in terms of its operation and reward. Job security was perceived positively but corruption/bad behavior in the public

service was most perceived negatively. This is attributed to employing unqualified staff in public service. According to Okojie (2022), employment in Nigeria's public sector is meant to align with civil service rules that uphold neutrality and professionalism, yet the practical realities often contradict this ideal. Employment also includes different forms and classifications permanent, temporary, contract, and informal each with distinct implications for job security, motivation, and performance.

Public Service in Abia State

Public service according to Uduma, Ogba, and Emerole (2015) is an organized institution of the State with all the basic features and principles of rational authority which defines its modus operandi as it is governed by rules and regulations. Abia State's public service is organized through its Ministries, Departments, and Agencies (MDAs), which are responsible for implementing government policies and delivering essential services across various sectors such as health, education, agriculture, and infrastructure. Each MDA plays a critical role in ensuring the effective functioning of the state's administrative machinery. The Executive Council, comprising the Governor, Deputy Governor, Secretary to the State Government, Chief of Staff, and Commissioners overseeing different ministries, serves as the highest decision-making body in the state. This council is pivotal in formulating and executing policies that drive the state's development agenda.

To modernize the public service, the Abia State Government launched the "Better Service Initiative," aiming to transform the public service into a more efficient and transparent entity. This initiative focuses on adopting best practices and leveraging technology to enhance service delivery.

Public service in Abia State revealed a range of administrative challenge. Ajunwa, Maina, and Musa (2025) in their study, capacity development and employee productivity in the Nigeria public

sector: a study of Abia state civil service commission, Umuahia. The researchers used chi-square for testing the hypotheses and they discovered that the capacity building enhances the quality-of-service delivery in the Abia State civil service commission, Umuahia and that lack of training, insufficient fund and lack of modern technologies are the major factors militating against capacity building of employees in the Abia State civil service commission, Umuahia.

Mukoro (2015) is of the opinion that effective labour employment in primary schools does not just happened by chance but through unpoliticized and articulated recruitment, and adequate recruitment without bias is required because development of a state or nation involves preparing the minds of young ones through suitable teachers who will tender them to know their roles in the society through quality decision programmes and quality public service delivery.

Methodology

In quantitative research, there are four (4) elements of research design such as, descriptive, correlational, causal comparative and experimental research. Here, the researcher adopted descriptive survey research. The descriptive research is adopted because, it is an appropriate choice when not much is known yet about the topic or problem. The descriptive research is statistical in nature and its research aim is to identify characteristics, frequencies, gauging public opinion on political and social topics. This equally enabled the researcher to narrate a given situation or circumstance within a certain period and place and obtaining data from the large population spread across the selected two Local Governments, Obingwa and Ohafia Local Government employees.

The study population comprised the employees of Ohafia and Obingwa Local Governments in Abia State, with the population of 2,291. Three hundred and twenty-six (326) employees were randomly sampled in Ohafia and Obingwa Local Government Areas of Abia State, using Taro Yamane's formula. Structured questionnaire was used as an instrument of data collection and was analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS). Hypotheses were tested using chi-square at 5% significant level. The primary data is structured questionnaire while the secondary data is collected through the use of textbooks, journals, articles, magazines, newspapers, government publications and internet- based materials.

Data Presentation, Analysis, and Discussion of Findings

DEMOGRAPHICS	Frequency	Percentage
SEX		
MALE	153	46.9
FEMALE	173	53.1
TOTAL	326	100.0
AGE		
21-30 YRS	35	10.7
31-40 YRS	172	52.8
41-50 YRS	90	27.6
51 YRS AND ABOVE	29	8.9
TOTAL	326	100.0
MARITAL STATUS		
SINGLE	54	16.6

MARRIED	216	66.3
DIVORCED	32	9.8
WIDOW/WOWER	24	7.4
TOTAL	326	100.0
EMPLOYMENT CATEGORY		
EDUCATIONAL DEPT	121	37.1
ADMIN STAFF	45	13.8
HEALTH DEPT	115	35.3
WORKS DEPT	42	12.9
5.00	3	.9
Total	326	100.0
EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION		
SSCE	21	6.4
NCE/OND	93	28.5
HND/B.Sc	93	28.5
MASTERS	79	24.2
PHD	40	12.3
Total	326	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

From the table 1 above it can be deduced that 53.1% of the respondents are females while 46.9% are males, about 52.8% are between the ages of 31-40 years while 27.6% are 41 – 50 years, 10.7% are between 21-30 years, and 8.9% are 51 years and above. The table also shows that most of the respondents are married, accounting for 66.3% of the total respondents while 16.6%, 9.8% and 7.4% are single, divorced and widow/widower respectively. Also, the distribution of the respondents according to their employment category showed that 37.1% are in the educational department, while 35.3%, 13.8%, and 12.9% are in the health department, admin staff, and works department respectively. The distribution of the respondents according to their educational qualification revealed that 28.5% of the respondents are HND/B.Sc holders while another 28.5%, 24.2%, 12.3% and 6.4% are NCE/OND, Masters, PhD and SSCE holders respectively.

Table 2: Recruitment Policy and Service Delivery

S/N	ITEMS	SA F (%)	A F (%)	UD F (%)	D F (%)	SD F (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Greater number of job recruitment are in the hands of the god- fathers and party affiliated members	237 (72.7)	51 (1.6)	29 (8.9)	4 (0.9)	6 (1.8)	4.56	0.84
2	There are public servants who are not seen around as a result of god-fathers who protect their jobs	129 (39.6)	169 (51.8)	15 (4.6)	10 (3.1)	3 (0.9)	4.26	0.76
3	Nobody is sure about credible, and properly advertised jobs in the local governments	113 (34.7)	174 (53.4)	33 (10.1)	3 (0.9)	3 (0.9)	4.19	0.73

4	Care-taker-committee is the tool used by the politicians to install their party acolytes in the recruitment process of the public service	86 (26.4)	151 (46.3)	75 (23.0)	10 (3.1)	4 (1.2)	3.94	0.85
5	Care-taker Committee use politics in recruiting than the principle of public service	109 (33.4)	127 (39)	81 (24.8)	6 (1.8)	3 (0.9)	4.02	0.86
6	Service deliveries like, adequate schools, good health centers and good roads are not within the reach of the communities	143 (43.9)	93 (28.5)	78 (23.9)	6 (1.8)	6 (1.8)	4.10	0.95

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The analysis from Table 2 above showed the respondents’ views on how the recruitment policy promoted service delivery in the study area. It can be seen that most of the respondents agree that greater number of job recruitment are in the hands of the god-fathers and party affiliated members (= 4.56, SD= 0.84). Also, most of the respondents agreed that there are public servants who are not seen around as a result of god-fathers who protect their jobs (= 4.26, SD= 0.76). In the same vein, most of the respondents agreed that nobody is sure about credible, and properly advertised jobs in the local government (= 4.19, SD= 0.73). Also, most of the respondents agree that care-taker committee is the tool used by the politicians to install their party acolytes in the recruitment process of the public service (= 3.94, SD= 0.85). Also, most of the respondents agree that care-taker committee used politics in recruitment than the principle of public service (= 4.02, SD= 0.86). Also, most of the respondents agree that service deliveries like, adequate schools, good health centers and good roads are not within the reach of the communities (= 4.10, SD= 0.95).

Table 3: Contending pressures faced by the public servants in the local governments

S/N	Item	SA F (%)	A F (%)	U F (%)	D F (%)	SD F (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.
13	The need for timely payment of salaries	164 (50.3)	96 (29.4)	54 (16.6)	12 (3.7)		4.25	0.87
14	The need for staff promotion exercise in the public service at the appropriate time	144 (44.2)	116 (35.6)	60 (18.4)	3 (0.9)	3 (0.9)	4.21	0.83
15	State Government consistently holding the allocations of the local government through the joint account, is a major problem.	102 (31.3)	149 (45.7)	69 (21.2)	3 (0.9)	3 (0.9)	4.06	0.80
16	When someone feels cheated in employment, it makes the person not to work properly	118 (36.2)	138 (42.3)	58 (17.8)	6 (1.8)	3 (0.9)	4.12	0.83
17	Areas that required manpower needs like, health centers, roads	87 (26.7)	152 (46.6)	72 (22.1)	12 (3.7)		3.97	0.80

	and education are ignored as a result of filling the pay-roll with ghost-workers							
18	Evidence of poor equipment in health sectors, education sectors and works sectors but heavy budget claims.	100 (30.7)	150 (46.0)	67 (20.6)	9 (2.8)		4.04	0.79

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Decision rule if mean is: 0 -1.49= Strongly Disagree; 1.5-2.49= Disagree; 2.5-3.49= Undecided; 3.5-4.49= Agree; 4.5-5.0= Strongly Agree

The analysis from Table 5.5 above showed the respondents' views on the contending pressures faced by the public servants in the study area. It can be seen that most of the respondents agree on the need for timely payment of salaries (= 4.25, SD= 0.87). Also, most of the respondents agree on the need for staff promotion exercise in the public service at the appropriate time (= 4.21, SD= 0.83). In the same vein, most of the respondents agree that state government consistently holding the allocations of the local government through the joint account, is a major problem (= 4.06, SD= 0.80). Also, most of the respondents agree that when someone feels cheated in employment, it makes the person not to work properly (= 4.12, SD= 0.83). Also, most of the respondents agree that areas that required manpower needs like, health centers, roads and education are ignored as a result of filling the pay-roll with ghost-workers (= 3.97, SD= 0.80). Also, most of the respondents agree on evidence of poor equipment in health sectors, education sectors and works sectors but heavy budget claims (= 4.04, SD= 0.79).

Table 4: Workable solutions that leads to merit-based employment.

S/N	ITEM	SA F (%)	A F (%)	UD F (%)	D F (%)	SD F (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.
19	There is need for evidence of actual number recruited in tandem with salary budgeted.	175 (53.7)	117 (35.9)	19 (5.8)	9 (2.8)	6 (1.8)	4.36	0.86
20	Timely auditing of number of staff members and performance assessment.	147 (45.1)	117 (35.9)	44 (13.5)	15 (4.6)	3 (0.9)	4.19	0.90
21	Inefficiency resulting from uneven replacement and posting in order to favour the political stalwarts, is a major problem	112 (34.4)	153 (46.9)	52 (16.0)	9 (2.8)		4.13	0.77
22	The need to deal with poor service delivery caused by unseen staff in primary schools, resulting from ghost-work in the system.	119 (36.5)	117 (35.9)	74 (22.7)	9 (2.8)	3 (0.9)	4.55	0.60
23	There is evidence of poor service delivery because of the	96 (29.4)	164 (54.3)	60 (18.4)	6 (1.8)		4.07	0.74

	recruitment based on knowing people in political seats							
24	The need to properly advertise the available job positions and proper conduct of examinations and timely offer of jobs	120 (36.8)	131 (40.2)	66 (20.2)	9 (2.8)		4.11	0.81

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The analysis from Table 4 above showed the respondents’ views on the workable propositions/solutions that would lead to merit-based employment. It can be seen that most of the respondents agree that there is need for evidence of actual number recruited in tandem with salary budgeted (= 4.36, SD= 0.86). Also, most of the respondents agree that timely auditing of numbers of staff members and performance assessment (= 4.19, SD= 0.90). In the same vein, most of the respondents agree that inefficiency resulting from uneven replacement and posting in order to favour the political stalwarts, is a major problem (= 4.13, SD= 0.77). Also, most of the respondents strongly agree on the need to deal with poor service delivery caused by unseen staff in primary schools, resulting from ghost-workers in the system (= 4.55, SD= 0.60). Also, most of the respondents agree that there is evidence of poor service delivery because of the recruitment based on knowing people in political seats (= 4.07, SD= 0.74). Also, most of the respondents agree on the need to properly advertise the available job positions and proper conduct of examinations and timely offer of jobs (= 4.11, SD= 0.81).

Test of Hypothesis

Ho₁: Recruitment policy has not promoted service delivery in Obingwa and Ohafia Local Governments in Abia State?

H₁: Recruitment policy has promoted service delivery in Obingwa and Ohafia Local Governments in Abia State?

Table 5.1 Recruitment policy and service delivery

Value	RQ 1
Chi-Square	81.373 ^a
Df	13
Asymp. Sig.	.000

Table 5.1 above showed that the calculated chi-square value of 81.373 is greater than the chi-square tabulated value of 22.362, hence, hence, the null hypothesis which states that recruitment policy has not promoted service delivery is hereby rejected. This implies that recruitment policy has promoted service delivery.

Hypothesis 2

Ho₂: There are no contending pressures faced by public servants in the local governments under investigation.

H1₂: There are contending pressures faced by public servants in the local governments under investigation.

Table 5.2 Contending pressure faced by public servants

Value	RQ 2
Chi-Square	43.667 ^b
Df	16
Asymp. Sig.	.000

Table 5.2 above showed that the calculated chi-square value of 43.667 is greater than the chi-square tabulated value of 26.296, hence, the null hypothesis which states that there are no contending pressures faced by public c servant in the local governments under investigation is hereby rejected. This implies that there are contending pressures faced by public servant in the local governments under investigation.

Hypothesis 3

H₀₃: There are no workable solutions that can lead to merit-based employment.

H₁₃: There are workable solutions that can lead to merit-based employment.

Table 5.3 Workable solution that can lead to merit-based employment.

Value	RQ 3
Chi-Square	94.000 ^b
Df	16
Asymp. Sig.	.000

Table 5.3 above showed that the calculated chi-square value of 94.000 is greater than the chi-square tabulated value of 26.296, hence, the null hypothesis which states that there are no workable solution that can lead to merit-based employment is hereby rejected. This implies that there are workable solutions that can lead to merit-based employment.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the politicization of employment and service delivery in Ohafia and Obingwa Local Government Areas. The discussion is hereby organized according to the major findings from the three research hypotheses in the study.

The findings showed that politicians’ influence over recruitment has affected service delivery. The influence of politicians over recruitment in public service has been a longstanding concern, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria, where political patronage often supersedes merit-based selection. Bashir (2025) in his study on the impact of the politicization of state government in Nigeria, highlights that political interference in recruitment practices has led to the appointment of less qualified personnel into key positions. This practice diminishes the overall efficiency of the public service and impairs the delivery of services to the citizens. Politicians often prioritize loyalty over competence, leading to a misalignment between the skills required for effective service

delivery and the capabilities of recruited individuals. Such practices have been particularly detrimental in sectors such as education and healthcare, where service quality is heavily reliant on the expertise of civil servants (Bashir, 2025).

Also, the findings showed that recruitment policy has promoted service delivery. Recruitment policies in the public sector play a pivotal role in enhancing service delivery, particularly when they are designed to align with the needs of citizens and the competencies required for effective public administration. One article that supports this view is Egeberg, Gornitzka, and Trondal, (2017) which showed that public administrations that practice merit-based recruitment of their personnel are significantly less marked by corruption than administrations that do not recruit in this manner. While we know a lot about how European Union member states score with regard to the degree of merit-based recruitment within their administrations, and also how the European Commission administration performs in this respect, recruitment practices within the increasing number of European Union regulatory (decentralized) agencies seem to remain a white spot in the literature so far. The article shows that European Union agencies seem to overwhelmingly apply meritocratic instruments when hiring people, regardless of their location. By ensuring that recruitment policies focus on the right qualifications and skills, governments have been able to enhance the overall quality of public services, making them more responsive to citizens' needs. This demonstrates how recruitment policies, when effectively implemented, foster the growth of a competent public service capable of delivering better outcomes. Further supporting this, Igbokwe-Ibeto et al. (2015) focus on the impact of manpower planning and development in Lagos State, Nigeria. They argue that a strategic recruitment policy that emphasizes the development of human resources in the public sector has led to notable improvements in service delivery. The study indicates that when recruitment is based on planned strategies that align with governmental objectives, it allows for a more efficient and effective civil service. This approach, they claim, enhances employee motivation, reduces turnover, and improves overall public sector performance, all of which are critical factors for service delivery in any nation. However, some studies suggest that recruitment policies, especially in developing countries, may not always have a positive impact on service delivery.

Additionally, Halligan (2021) examines the political dynamics in the public service from a comparative perspective and argues that while politicization does exist, the extent to which it creates pressure can be mitigated by a strong institutional framework and adherence to bureaucratic norms. He posits that a well-structured public service can maintain its integrity despite political challenges, suggesting that local governments can better manage such pressures with the right institutional safeguards.

Also, the findings showed that there are workable solutions that can lead to merit-based employment. The idea that merit-based employment in the Nigerian public sector is achievable is supported by several studies that emphasize reforms and improvements in recruitment practices. The need to hire based on merit cannot be underrated in public service, highlighting that reforms, such as the introduction of standardized selection criteria and transparent recruitment procedures, can help promote merit-based hiring.

Conclusion

This study offers important insights into the politicization of employment and its impact on service delivery in Ohafia and Obingwa Local Government Areas. The findings highlighted key issues and their implications for the local government systems in Abia State. First, the study demonstrated that political interference in the recruitment process significantly undermines service delivery. The results underscore how political interference disrupts the efficiency of public service, emphasizing the need for reforms that protect recruitment processes from political manipulation to enhance public sector effectiveness.

Recommendation

It is crucial to insulate the recruitment process from political interference. A recommendation is to establish an independent recruitment body at the local government level that operates with transparency and accountability. This body should be tasked with overseeing the recruitment and selection process, ensuring that appointments are based on merit rather than political affiliation. Furthermore, the implementation of stringent policies and procedures, such as blind recruitment and standardized evaluation criteria, will reduce the scope for political influence in the hiring process. Stakeholders, including political leaders, must also be educated on the long-term benefits of a merit-based system in improving local government efficiency and service delivery.

While the recruitment policy has shown some positive impact on service delivery, it is essential to further enhance its effectiveness. Local governments should review and update their recruitment policies regularly to ensure alignment with best practices in human resource management. This includes developing clear and well-documented recruitment procedures that prioritize merit and qualifications over other considerations. Additionally, the recruitment process should incorporate feedback mechanisms from employees and the communities served, enabling continuous improvements in the policy to better meet the needs of both the workforce and the citizens.

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